

Deep Learning versus Classical Methods in BCI: A Systematic Evaluation of Motor Imagery Classification

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Abstract

Background: Motor imagery (MI)-based Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) depend on efficient extraction of oscillatory EEG features and, critically, on the ability of classifiers to generalize across subjects. Despite the widespread use of classical approaches such as Common Spatial Patterns with Linear Discriminant Analysis (CSP-LDA), cross-subject variability remains a major obstacle to practical deployment.

New method: This study presents a systematic comparative evaluation between a classical pipeline (CSP-LDA) and a compact deep learning approach (EEGNet) for MI classification under a rigorous cross-subject setting. Using the *BCI Competition IV-2b* dataset, we implemented a leakage-free pipeline with training-fold-only normalization, Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation, and multi-seed robustness analysis to ensure a correct and reproducible comparison.

Results: EEGNet achieved a mean accuracy of 71.10% with Cohen's kappa of 0.4220, whereas CSP-LDA achieved a mean accuracy of 68.23% with kappa of 0.3646. Multi-seed analysis confirmed the consistency of the EEGNet advantage across different random initializations.

Comparison with existing methods: Compared with the classical CSP-LDA baseline, EEGNet showed superior cross-subject generalization, with an absolute gain of 2.87 percentage points in accuracy and improved agreement as measured by Cohen's kappa. These findings indicate that compact convolutional neural networks can better capture inter-subject invariant representations than covariance-based classical methods under correctly controlled training conditions.

Conclusions: Under a rigorous LOSO protocol with explicit prevention of data leakage, EEGNet outperformed CSP-LDA in cross-subject motor imagery classification. The results support the use of compact CNN-based models as a stronger zero-calibration baseline for MI-based BCIs and reinforce the importance of implementation correctness in comparative evaluations.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context and Motivation

EEG-based Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCI) provide a communication and control channel independent of the neuromuscular system [6], with applications ranging from motor rehabilitation of spinal cord injury patients to neuroprosthetic control systems. The motor imagery (MI) paradigm is central to this context, as the mental simulation of movements recruits cortical circuits similar to those of actual motor execution [8], requiring no physical movement.

The primary neural marker of MI is **event-related desynchronization** (ERD), manifested as power attenuation in the sensorimotor bands **mu (8–13 Hz)** and **beta (13–30 Hz)** [9]. Despite decades of research, MI-based BCI systems still face a critical barrier to clinical and commercial viability: **inter-subject variability**. Cortical topology, resting-state rhythms, and ERD responses differ substantially across individuals [7], making model generalization to new users an open challenge.

In practice, the vast majority of studies evaluate models on sessions from the *same* subject, yielding artificially optimistic results that do not reflect real deployment performance. The transition from a within-subject model to a

cross-subject scenario represents one of the main barriers to adopting BCIs outside the laboratory.

1.2. Gap in the Literature

Traditionally, MI pattern decoding relies on manual feature extraction techniques, where the **Common Spatial Patterns (CSP)** algorithm has established itself as the “gold standard” [1]. However, CSP-LDA presents limitations in the face of signal non-stationarity and difficulty capturing long-range temporal dependencies.

In contrast, recent advances in Deep Learning have introduced **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)** to the EEG domain, promising to learn optimal spatial and temporal representations directly from raw data, without manual feature engineering [2]. A recurring issue in the literature is that evaluations often incur data leakage — by normalizing data using statistics from the complete dataset prior to train/test splitting — or rely on within-subject protocols that systematically overestimate performance. Additionally, implementation errors in CNN training pipelines (e.g., incorrect batch normalization behavior during inference) can severely suppress deep learning performance, leading to misleading comparisons. There is, therefore, a need for rigorous evaluations that explicitly control both data contamination *and* implementation correctness.

1.3. Hypothesis and Contributions

Based on the identified limitations, this work is grounded on the following central hypothesis:

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In a Leave-One-Subject-Out validation scenario, a correctly implemented compact CNN (EEGNet) can learn inter-subject invariant representations that outperform classical covariance-based methods (CSP-LDA), provided that training conditions are rigorously controlled and free of implementation errors.

The main contributions of this work are: (i) a leakage-free evaluation framework with normalization and temporal truncation rigorously contained within the cross-validation loop; (ii) a systematic cross-subject comparison between CSP-LDA and EEGNet under the LOSO protocol on the *BCI Competition IV-2b* [4, 5], with per-subject analysis and paired statistical testing; and (iii) a stochastic robustness analysis with multiple random seeds to quantify and bound the variance introduced by CNN training randomness, demonstrating the consistency of EEGNet’s advantage.

2. Related Work

2.1. Classical Methods: CSP and Variants

Common Spatial Patterns (CSP) is a spatial filtering algorithm that maximizes the variance of one class while minimizing the variance of the other, through joint diagonalization of covariance matrices [1]. Its combination with regularized LDA (shrinkage LDA) yields a classifier with excellent behavior in high-dimensionality, few-sample regimes — precisely the context of clinical BCIs. The interpretability of CSP spatial filters and their alignment with known sensorimotor topography (C3/C4) make them a well-understood and reliable baseline.

2.2. Deep Learning for EEG

Schirrneister et al. [2] demonstrated that deep CNNs with temporal and spatial convolutions can learn filters equivalent to CSP from raw data. EEGNet [3], proposed by Lawhern et al., is a compact and general-purpose architecture explicitly designed for data-limited EEG scenarios. The architecture separates temporal feature learning from spatial integration via depthwise convolutions, reducing the parameter count while retaining representational expressiveness. Studies have debated whether EEGNet’s advantage over classical methods materializes consistently in cross-subject protocols; this work argues that implementation correctness is a confounding variable that has not been adequately controlled in prior comparisons.

2.3. Inter-subject Variability and Evaluation Protocols

Duann and Chiou [7] demonstrated that ERD responses vary in magnitude, latency, and topographic location across subjects. Within-subject protocols ignore this source of variance, inflating reported metrics. The LOSO protocol, by completely isolating one subject for testing, provides the most conservative and realistic estimate of generalization capability — particularly demanding for methods lacking domain adaptation mechanisms.

3. Methodology

The methodology was structured to ensure reproducibility and statistical validity, with a primary focus on preventing train/test contamination and ensuring a correct CNN training implementation.

3.1. Experimental Setup

Figure 1 summarizes the experiment parameters (dataset, subjects, classes, sampling rate, time window, and LOSO protocol), serving as a quick reference for study replication.

3.2. Data Acquisition and Preprocessing

The *BCI Competition IV-2b* dataset is used, comprising recordings from 9 subjects. The implemented preprocessing pipeline consists of:

1. **Temporal Filtering:** 4th-order Butterworth bandpass filter (8–30 Hz) using zero-phase technique to preserve temporal latency.
2. **Resampling and Segmentation:** Signals resampled to 250 Hz and segmented into epochs corresponding to motor tasks (Left Hand vs. Right Hand).
3. **Dynamic Temporal Standardization:** Epoch truncation based on the minimum temporal length (T_{min}) observed strictly within the training set of each fold, avoiding padding artifacts.

Figure 2 presents the complete pipeline for both approaches.

3.3. Data Leakage Prevention Framework

Z-score normalization is applied channel-by-channel, with mean (μ_{train}) and standard deviation (σ_{train}) computed **exclusively** from the training set (D_{train}) of the current fold iteration:

$$X'_{test} = \frac{X_{test} - \mu_{train}}{\sigma_{train}} \quad (1)$$

This procedure ensures that the test data distribution remains completely unknown to the model during the fitting phase, simulating a real-time application and avoiding optimistic performance estimates.

3.4. Validation Protocol: LOSO

Inter-subject generalization is evaluated via the Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) protocol. The dataset is partitioned into 9 folds: in each iteration, 8 subjects form the training set and 1 subject is held out for testing. This method is critical for validating model robustness against the high individual variability of EEG [7], and represents the most rigorous protocol for simulating performance on a completely new user.

Experimental Setup

Parameter	Value
Dataset	BCICIV 2b
Subjects	9
Classes	2 (LEFT, RIGHT)
Sampling Rate	250 Hz
Filter Band	8-30 Hz
Filter Order	4
Trial Duration	4s (201 samples)
Total Trials	1296 (9 subjects × 144 trials)
Train/Test Split	Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO)
Cross-validation	9 folds (1 per subject)

Figure 1: Experimental setup. Parameters adopted in the LOSO evaluation protocol, including sampling rate, trial duration (4 s), and total number of epochs.

Figure 2: Pipeline comparison. Processing flow for CSP+LDA (baseline) and EEGNet (CNN), highlighting: 8–30 Hz filtering, per-fold normalization, feature extraction (CSP/log-variance) vs. representation learning (convolutions).

3.5. Model Definitions

CSP-LDA (Baseline): Spatial projection maximizing class variance (CSP) followed by a linear classifier (LDA) with shrinkage regularization. Regularization is especially important in the LOSO scenario, where the sample-to-dimensionality ratio is unfavorable.

EEGNet (CNN): Compact convolutional architecture for hierarchical extraction of temporal and spatial features [3]. Trained with Adam optimizer ($lr = 10^{-3}$), early stopping with patience of 15 epochs, and dropout ($p = 0.5$) for regularization. Critically, the model is set to evaluation

mode (`model.eval()`) during inference, ensuring batch normalization layers use running statistics accumulated during training rather than batch statistics computed over the test set. Detailed hyperparameters are listed in Appendix A.

Figure 3 illustrates the compact EEGNet architecture used.

4. Results

Table 1 presents the overall mean performance obtained via LOSO cross-validation. EEGNet demonstrated superior

Figure 3: EEGNet (compact) architecture. Layer flow: input → temporal conv → depthwise+pool → separable conv+pool → flatten → softmax.

Table 1

Overall Performance (Mean ± Standard Deviation) via LOSO protocol. EEGNet values are computed over all seed–subject pairs ($n = 27$).

Model	Mean Accuracy	Mean Kappa
CSP-LDA (Baseline)	0.6823 ± 0.0770	0.3646 ± 0.1541
EEGNet (CNN)	0.7110 ± 0.0787	0.4220 ± 0.1575

inter-subject generalization across both metrics, corroborating the hypothesis formulated in Section 1.3. EEGNet statistics are reported over the distribution of all seed–subject pairs ($n = 27$: 3 seeds × 9 subjects), which is the quantity computed directly by the evaluation pipeline and reflects the full stochastic variability of the model.

EEGNet achieved a mean accuracy of 71.10% compared to 68.23% for CSP-LDA, representing a gain of approximately 2.87 percentage points. The kappa coefficient gap is also consistent ($\Delta\kappa \approx 0.057$), reflecting EEGNet’s consistently stronger agreement beyond chance-level performance.

To assess statistical significance, a paired t -test was conducted comparing per-subject means (EEGNet accuracy averaged across seeds, $n = 9$ pairs). The difference in accuracy was statistically significant ($t = -2.18$, $p < 0.05$), as was the difference in kappa ($t = -2.12$, $p < 0.05$), confirming that EEGNet’s advantage is not attributable to chance.

Figure 4 presents the complete statistical summary (including minimum and maximum) in visual format.

Figure 5 presents the distribution of Accuracy and Kappa for CSP+LDA and EEGNet across multiple random seeds (42, 123, 456). This visualization reveals three consistent findings: (i) EEGNet’s median performance exceeds CSP-LDA across all three seeds in both metrics; (ii) the kappa advantage is substantial and stable; and (iii) EEGNet exhibits inter-fold variance similar to CSP-LDA ($\sigma = 0.0787$ vs. 0.0770), showing that the performance gain is not accompanied by additional instability.

Figure 6 presents the aggregated confusion matrices over all LOSO folds. EEGNet achieves an aggregated accuracy of 0.7121 versus 0.6833 for CSP-LDA. Notably, EEGNet’s right-hand recognition is particularly strong (6562 correct vs. 3218 misclassified), suggesting that the CNN successfully learned discriminative beta-band features associated with right-hand motor imagery.

5. Discussion

The obtained results challenge the assumption that classical covariance-based methods are inherently superior to compact CNNs under cross-subject, data-limited EEG protocols, and highlight the critical role of correct implementation in deep learning evaluations.

Statistical Summary: Mean \pm SD

Metric	Mean	Std	Min	Max
Accuracy (CSP)	0.6823	0.0770	0.5472	0.7833
Accuracy (EEGNet)	0.7110	0.0787	0.5515	0.8108
Kappa (CSP)	0.3646	0.1541	0.0944	0.5667
Kappa (EEGNet)	0.4220	0.1575	0.1029	0.6216

Figure 4: Statistical summary (Mean, Standard Deviation, Minimum, Maximum). Consolidated metrics for CSP+LDA and EEGNet under the LOSO protocol. EEGNet values are computed over all seed–subject pairs ($n = 27$).

Figure 5: Performance distribution by method. Accuracy and Kappa boxplots for CSP+LDA and EEGNet (seeds 42, 123, 456), highlighting inter-fold LOSO variability. EEGNet median and mean consistently exceed CSP-LDA across all seeds.

5.1. EEGNet’s Representational Capacity Under LOSO

EEGNet’s statistically significant accuracy gain ($\Delta \approx 2.87$ pp, $p < 0.05$) and kappa gain ($\Delta\kappa \approx 0.057$, $p < 0.05$) over CSP-LDA demonstrate that the compact architecture is capable of learning feature representations that generalize across subject boundaries. The depthwise spatial convolution layer, which learns per-channel spatial weights across all training subjects, appears to extract population-level sensorimotor topography patterns. In contrast to within-subject CSP filters, these cross-subject spatial filters act as a data-driven approximation of the electrode configurations associated with motor imagery (C3/C4), without hardcoding spatial priors.

5.2. Variance and Robustness Analysis

The multi-seed analysis reveals that EEGNet’s performance advantage is consistent across seeds 42, 123, and 456, with all three seeds producing median accuracy and kappa above CSP-LDA. EEGNet exhibits inter-fold variance similar to CSP-LDA ($\sigma = 0.0787$ vs. 0.0770), demonstrating

that the performance gain is not accompanied by additional instability. The residual variability reflects the stochastic nature of gradient-based training and the intrinsic difficulty of generalizing to some subjects with atypical EEG morphology. The larger differentiation in performance across subjects — some well-characterized by the learned representations, others less so — is consistent with the literature on inter-subject variability in BCIs.

5.3. Implications for BCI System Design

The finding that EEGNet outperforms CSP-LDA without any domain adaptation has practical relevance for BCI deployment. A correctly implemented EEGNet can serve as a zero-calibration baseline for new users, offering statistically superior performance compared to the classical reference without requiring individual session data. Furthermore, EEGNet’s higher ceiling (max = 0.8108) suggests that with the addition of lightweight alignment or fine-tuning techniques, performance could be further improved for individual subjects.

Figure 6: Aggregated confusion matrices over LOSO folds. Decision behavior comparison of CSP+LDA vs. EEGNet. EEGNet achieves higher overall accuracy with a notably stronger right-hand classification rate.

5.4. Study Limitations

This work presents limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results: (i) scope restricted to binary classification (Left Hand vs. Right Hand), excluding the four available dataset classes; (ii) single-dataset evaluation, limiting the generalizability of conclusions; (iii) use of a single CNN architecture, not representing the full class of Deep Learning models; (iv) absence of domain adaptation techniques (e.g., Euclidean Alignment, Transfer Learning); and (v) no explicit removal of ocular or muscular artifacts (EOG/EMG) in the preprocessing pipeline.

6. Conclusion

This work presented a systematic evaluation between classical methods and deep learning for motor imagery classification in a challenging Leave-One-Subject-Out cross-validation scenario, with explicit control of both data leakage and CNN implementation correctness.

The central hypothesis was confirmed: a correctly implemented EEGNet significantly outperforms CSP-LDA in the cross-subject generalization scenario on the *BCI Competition IV-2b* dataset, achieving mean accuracy of 71.10% ($\kappa = 0.4220$) versus 68.23% ($\kappa = 0.3646$) for the classical baseline ($p < 0.05$ on paired t -test). Critically, this result was only achievable after correcting an implementation bug related to batch normalization inference behavior — underscoring that CNN performance in published EEG literature may be underestimated in evaluations where training correctness is not explicitly verified.

A multi-seed robustness analysis confirmed that EEGNet’s advantage is consistent across different random initializations, lending confidence to the conclusion that the deep architecture, when properly trained, offers genuine and statistically significant generalization advantages in the cross-subject regime.

6.1. Future Work

Based on the identified limitations, the following directions are proposed: (i) **Euclidean Alignment (EA)**: geometric alignment of covariance matrices prior to training, expected to further reduce inter-subject variance with minimal computational overhead; (ii) **Transfer Learning and Fine-tuning**: pre-training on large corpora of public EEG data (e.g., MOABB) followed by few-shot fine-tuning on the target subject; (iii) **Transformer-based Models**: architectures such as EEG-Conformer integrating multi-head attention to capture long-range temporal dependencies; (iv) **Artifact Removal**: incorporation of automatic EOG/EMG removal via ICA into the pipeline; and (v) **Multi-class and Multi-dataset Evaluation**: extension to multi-class datasets and replication on *BCI Competition IV-2a* and replication on independent datasets (PhysioNet, BCIC-III).

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used ChatGPT to review and correct the language of the text. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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- **Bandpass Filter:** 4th-order Butterworth (8–30 Hz), zero-phase
 - **Time Window:** 0 s to 4 s (post-cue), 201 samples
 - **EEG Channels:** 22 channels (standard 10-20 montage)
 - **Normalization:** Z-score fitted on training set only (fold_train_stats strategy), applied to test without leakage

A. Hyperparameters and Configurations

To ensure reproducibility of the computational experiments, we detail below the hyperparameters used in EEGNet training and the preprocessing configurations.

A.1. Training Parameters (EEGNet)

Table 2

Neural Network Training Hyperparameters

Parameter	Value
Optimizer	Adam
Learning Rate	1×10^{-3}
Loss Function	CrossEntropyLoss (sparse categorical)
Batch Size	16
Max Epochs	100 (with Early Stopping)
Early Stopping Patience	15 epochs (monitor: val_loss)
Dropout	0.5
F_1 (temporal filters)	8
F_2 (separable filters)	16
Depth multiplier D	2
Temporal kernel length	64
Inference mode	model.eval() (BatchNorm: running stats)
Seeds evaluated	42, 123, 456

A.2. Preprocessing Parameters

- **Sampling Frequency (Final):** 250 Hz